

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF ABATTOIR EFFLUENT ON THE IYI EKE STREAM AFIKPO, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research assessed the environmental impact of Abattoir effluent on Iyi Eke Stream Afikpo, Nigeria. Water samples were collected and analysed monthly from five (5) sampling points along the stream at interval of 25m from January to June, 2024 in accordance with American Public Health Association (APHA). This process accommodated variation in time and frequency of discharge of the effluent and dilution effect of precipitation. The upstream samples were the controls. Water parameters analysed were pH, Temperature, colour, DO, Zn, Pb, Al, Hg, BOD, COD, TDS, Nitrate, Phosphorous, Ammonia, Total Coliform count and E-Coli. Descriptive statistic and ANOVA were used to analyse the data. From the findings, most physico-chemical parameters were within the permissible limits of WHO and NSDWQ standards while all the concentrations of biological and heavy metals parameters exceeded the permissible limits. The study revealed that biological and heavy metal parameters were the critical pollutants of Iyi Eke stream. This implies that the discharge of abattoir effluent into Iyi Eke stream contributed to large scale biological and heavy metal pollution of the stream. The study recommends biological treatment using anaerobic digester before being discharged into water body. The study further recommends effective waste management practices within the abattoir environment and that Iyi Eke stream water should be treated before use because of its high level of pollution. These practices will protect the environment and secure public health.

Keywords: Abattoir, Effluent, Discharge, Environmental Impact, Assessment, Iyi Eke Stream.

Introduction

Iyi Eke stream is a vital component of the ecosystem in Afikpo Urban, providing water for irrigation, drinking and other uses as well as habitat for diverse range of aquatic species. The stream water quality is a critical indicator of its overall health and any pollution or degradation can have far reaching consequences for both human health and the environment. One of the primary sources of pollution in Iyi Eke Stream is the discharge of Abattoir effluent. Abattoir effluent is made up of liquid/solid waste from slaughter house (a place where animals are slaughtered for human consumption). This effluent contains contaminated fluids, organic matter such as faeces, urine, blood, carcasses, undiluted foods, loose meat etc. this large volume of waste water could contain high levels of pollutants such as Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Suspended Solid (TSS) and heavy metals. These pollutants can have devastating effects on the rivers ecosystem including changes to water temperature, pH level and dissolved oxygen levels which can be determinant to aquatic life (Pandey and Tiwari, 2021).

The direct effects of Abattoir effluent on aquatic biodiversity are profound. The alteration of habitat quality and the introduction of toxins can lead to shifts in species decline or disappear (Mizuguchi *et al.*, 2021). This loss of biodiversity can destabilize ecosystems, reducing their resilience and ability to provide essential services such as water filtration, habitat provision and nutrient cycling (Diaz *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the bioaccumulation of toxins within aquatic food webs can have cascading effects, affecting higher trophic levels, including fish and aquatic mammals (Liu *et al.*, 2019).

The implications of abattoir effluent on human health are also a critical concern. Contaminated water bodies can serve as reservoirs for pathogens and toxins, posing risks to communities relying on these water sources for drinking, recreation and agriculture (Kumar and Singh, 2020). Consumption of contaminated fish and seafood can lead to severe health issues, including gastrointestinal diseases and long-term exposure effects from bioaccumulated toxins. The economic impact of these health risks, alongside the degradation of aquatic ecosystems and the services they provide, can be significant. A global study by the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that using polluted water either for bathing, drinking and other uses causes 250 million cases of gastro enteric upper respiratory disease, typhoid, cholera and other water borne diseases annually (Nwankwo et al., 2022).

The implications of Abattoir effluent on aquatic ecosystem are multifaceted, encompassing water quality degradation, nutrient loading, biodiversity loss, and human health risks. It is critical to implement effective waste management strategies and treatment processes to mitigate the detrimental effects of these effluents on aquatic environments. Despite extensive studies on impact of Abattoir effluents discharge into the streams, there is limited research on its effect on ecology. This research sought to bridge the gap. With the current focus on sustainability and scarcity of water, every drop of water should ideally be reclaimed and this has already been achieved in some cases (Jimoh et al, 2022). This study assessed the level of toxicity of the activities of Abattoir effluents on Iyi Eke stream and potentiality to those that use it. Moving forward, collaborative efforts among industries, governments, and communities are vital to protect and restore aquatic ecosystems affected by abattoir effluent.

The Research Objectives

The objectives of the study include the following:

- i. to assess the concentration of physico-chemical, biological and heavy metals parameters in Iyi Eke stream.
- ii. to compare measured values with WHO and NSDWQ standards.
- iii. to evaluate the potential health and ecological risks.

Materials

Water Samples

Sampling strategy

The sampling strategy used in this study involved collecting water samples from abattoir discharge point, upstream and downstream at interval of 25m.

Sampling

Water samples were collected using pre-cleaned polyethylene bottles and stored in ice coolers to prevent bacterial growth and were taken to Home water laboratory, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State for analysis according to the standard method of American Public Health Association (APHA, 1992).

Chemical Parameter Analysed

pH Determination

pH is a measure of the H⁺ concentration. It is expressed mathematically as $pH = \text{Log}(H^+)$. PH value ranges from acidic (1-6.8) through neutral (6.8-7.8) to basic (7.9-14). Therefore, PH determines the acidic or alkalinity (basicity) of water.

Method:

The method used to determine pH value is the electrometrically using glass electrons.

Procedure:

1. A pH meter was warmed for 15-20 minutes. The electrode was removed from the distilled water and wiped dry.
2. The pH meter was standardized using the buffer solution at a temperature of between 20°C to 25°C.
3. The pH knob was switched off on the electrode from the second buffer. Removed and rinsed thoroughly and then wiped with tissue paper.
4. The electrode was inserted into the sample and the power restored, then the reading of the scale was taken.
5. The electrode was finally rinsed and stored, immersed in distilled water.

DO and BOD Determination

The biological oxygen demand is an empirical test in which standardized laboratory procedures are used to determine the relative oxygen requirement of waste water. The test measure the oxygen required for the bio-chemical degradation or biological degradation of organic materials and the oxygen used to oxidize inorganic materials such as sulphide and ferrous iron while the dissolved oxygen (DO) serves as a means of water control. The level of DO in water determines the microbiological plant and animal contents and also its ability for sustaining the life of fishes and other aquatic organisms.

Procedure: The dissolved oxygen (DO) of the sample was tested for the day the samples were collected. The samples were initially used to rinse the BOD bottles and were filled up by ensuring no air bubbles remained in the bottle. 2ml of alkali diiodide-acid reagent was also added. The bottle was capped and shaken, the sample then formed brownish to whitish precipitate which was allowed to settle until it made up 100ml. 2ml sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) was also added. 200ml of the samples were measured into a conical flask and titrated with sodium thiosulphate (0.025N) until a pale yellow colour was formed, titration continued until the sample becomes colourless. The volume of the sodium thiosulphate used for the titration was noted. BOD difference between DO, on the first day and DO₅ after 5 days. Therefore $BOD = \frac{(DO_1 - DO_5) \times \text{volume of BOD bottle}}{\text{ml of sample used}}$

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) Determination

Procedure: 400mg of sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) was measured and placed in a reflux flask. 20ml of the sample and 20ml of distilled water was added and mixed, the 10ml of standard potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) solution and glass beads are already treated to 600°C for an hour. The flask was then attached to the reflux condenser and 300ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 containing H2804 was added, mixing thoroughly while adding the acid. The mixture was refluxed for an hour, cooled and the condenser was washed with distilled water. The mixture was distilled for about 15 minutes with distilled water and cooled to a room temperature. Three (3) drops of ferrion indicator was added and the mixture was titrated with $Fe(NH)$ to a colour change from blue-green to a reddish brown. A blank consisting of 20ml of distilled water was refluxed in the same manner together with the reagent.

Therefore the COD was calculated a $COD = \frac{(a-b)N \times 8000}{\text{ml of sample}}$

Where, N = Normality of titrate

A= ml titrant for blank

B= ml titrant for sample

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Procedure: 250mls of water sample was filtered and then evaporated to dryness in a conical flask using the oven. After the evaporation, the residue in the beaker was then measured to get the total dissolved solids (TDS) in ml/l.

This was done by subtracting the difference in the weight of the flask before and after the oven drying.

Nitrate Determination

Procedure:

A known volume (50ml) of the sample was pipetted into a porcelain dish and evaporated to dryness on a hot water bath. 2ml of phenol Disulphuric acid was added to dissolve the residue by constant stirring with a glass rod. Concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide and distilled water was added with stirring to make it alkaline. This was filtered into a Nessler's tube and made up to 50ml with distilled water. The absorbance was read at 410nm using UV-spectrophotometer Apel-Japan, Model No: PD-3000 UV after the development of colour.

$$\text{Nitrate concentration} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{concentration of standard}}{\text{Absorbance of standard}}$$

Procedure used for Biological Analysis

Total coliform MPN Test and Escherichia Coli (E. coli) Determination.

The total coliform MPN (Most Probable Number) test is a statistical estimation of the concentration of coliform organisms present in 100ml of the sample. Coliform organisms comprise of the entire aerobic, anaerobic, facultative, gram-negative, non-spore forming rod shaped bacteria which ferment lactose with gas formation within 48hrs at 35°C.

Methods for Calculation of MPN:

The MPN model or Thomas approximate method.

Procedure:

Specified volumes of water sample are added to sterile fermentation tubes or bottles containing lauryl tryptose broth, and stored at 35± 0.5°C in an incubator for 24 hours. Each tube is gently swirled and examined for heavy growth, gas production in a submerged inverted tube within the test vessel, or acid production indicated by formation of a yellow colour when bromocresol purple has been added to the medium. If there is no evidence of growth, gas or acid production, the sample are observed again after another 24hours of incubation. A positive presumptive reaction is established if there is gas production or acidic growth in the tubes within 48 hours.

In order to classify the coliform into those of faecal origin and those derived from non-faecal sources, the confirmatory test is performed. All the tubes which show evidence of-gas formation or acid production are regarded as positive tubes. These positive tubes are sub-cultured into an E. coli medium at 44°C for 24hours. The E. coli medium is used to encourage the growth of E. coli while the growth of other coliform bacteria is suppressed.

Determination of Nitrate (nitrogen trioxide, NO₃)

Nitrogen trioxide, NO₃ (nitrate) content can be determined by the following methods: screening by the ultraviolet spectrophotometry, ion chromatographic method, nitrate electrode method and cadmium reduction method.

Determination of Metals

Digestion of water sample:

The water samples were thoroughly mixed by shaking. 50ml of the sample was transferred into a glass beaker and 5.0ml of concentrated nitrate acid was added. The beaker with the content was placed on a hot plate and evaporated down to about 20ml. On cooling, the sample was filtered through using Whatman no.42 filter paper to remove some insoluble material that could clog the atomizer. The water sample was stored separately in a reagent bottle for elemental analysis using Varian Spectra AA 55B Atomic Absorption Spectrometer air-acetylene and Nitrous oxide flame.

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Technique

AAS is a technique which makes use of absorption spectrometry to assess the concentration of an analytic in sample. It requires standard solutions to establish the relationship between measured absorbance and the analytic concentration, and relies on Beer-Lambert law. It is commonly used for determining the concentration of a particular metal element in a sample. In their element form, metals will absorb ultraviolet light and get excited. Each metal has a characteristic wavelength that will be absorbed. The AAS instrument look for a particular metal of focusing a beam of UV light at a specific wavelength through a flame and into a detector. The sample of interest is aspirated into the flame. If that metal is present in the sample, it will absorb some of the light, thus reduce its intensity. The instrument measures the change in intensity. A computer data system converts the change in intensity into an absorbance.

Laboratory Analysis

The following pollutant indicators, pH, Temperature, Colour, TDS, Nitrate, Phosphorus, Ammonia, DO, BOD, COD, Total Coliform count and E-coli were analysed. Also analysed were heavy metals such as: Zinc, Lead, Aluminium and Mercury.

Result and Discussion

Data Analysis

Data for physico-chemical parameters were compared between mean values of parameters collected during dry season and that of the water samples collected during raining season using one-way ANOVA Test.

Table 3.1: ANOVA Table

Between samples	Different sum of square	Degree of freedom	Variance estimate
Between samples	288203.2	7	4117.89
Within samples	118112.71	48	2460.68
Total	406315.91	55	43632.57

With sample degree of freedom = Total degree of freedom minus between samples degree of freedom = 55-7=48

$$\text{Calculated F} = \frac{\text{Greater Variance estimate}}{\text{Less variance estimate}} = \frac{4117.89}{2460.68} = 16.73$$

3.2 Analysis of ANOVA Results

Analysis of ANOVA results based on some physico-chemical parameters with respect to temperature and pH between effluents values of dry season and that of raining season from the five (5) different sampling points along the stream did not show any significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The mean values pH of the effluent during the dry season was 7.3 and that of raining season was 7.4. This parameter fell within WHO and NSDWQ standards (i.e. 6.5 to 8.5).

The mean temperature values of the effluents during the dry season was 32°C while that of raining season was 31°C

S/N	Parameters	WHO 201	NSDWQ	Station A (control)	Station B	Station C	Station D	Station E	Remark
1	pH	6.5 – 8.5	6.5 – 8.5	6.5	7.8	7.4	7.3	7.1	Okay
2	Temperature °C	40°C	Ambient	28.9	30.5	30.8	32.2	30.1	Okay
3	Colour (TCU)		15	12	25	23	19	16	Point A okay Other not okay
4	DO (Mg/l)	6.0	6.32	120	54	63	75	115	Okay
5	TDS (Mg/l)	500	500	48	65	37	39	41	Okay
6	Nitrate (Mg/l)	50	50	27.465	35.346	36.723	36.854	33.256	okay
7	Ammonia (NH ₃)	0.5	-	0.15	0.26	0.25	0.23	0.21	Okay
8	Phosphorus (Mg/l)	5	-	64.526	76.162	64.234	64.875	66.143	Okay
9	BOD (Mg/l)	Less than 5	Less than 5	38.4	172.0	164.0	162.6	158.2	Not okay
10	COD (Mg/l)	10.00	-	182.66	230.00	189.64	176.23	148.50	Not okay
11	Zinc (PPM)	0.10	0.2	2.814	5.632	4.932	4.844	4.400	Not Okay
12	Lead (PPM)	0.01	0.01	0.421	0.465	0.432	0.420	0.411	Not Okay
13	Aluminium (PPM)	0.10	0.2	2.814	5.632	4.932	4.844	4.400	Not Okay
14	Mercury (PPM)	0.001	0.001	0.032	0.054	0.045	0.044	0.041	Not Okay

15	Total coliform count (MPN/100m/l)	0.2	10	13	28	23	21	18	Not Okay
16	E-coli	0	0	9	37	28	26	22	Not Okay

Table 3.2: Mean concentrations of physico-chemical, microbial and heavy metals parameters analysed on five stations for January to June, 2024.

Discussion

pH

The mean pH values ranged from 6.5 to 7.8. this showed that the stream, pH value is within the WHO and NSDWQ guidelines values of 6.5 to 8.5 (WHO, 2017) and (NSDWQ, 2007). This implies that aquatic organisms in the water will not be affected by the pH concentration.

Fig. 3.1: Mean pH values for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Temperature

Temperature measured for all samples of water within the study area are presented in Table 3.1. The mean temperature of water in all stations for January to June, 2024 ranged from 28.9⁰ to 32.2⁰. The mean temperature values of the water samples were within the WHO guidelines value of 40⁰C (WHO, 2017). This means that the temperature is good, enhancing growth of micro-organism in the water. This may increase taste, odour and corrosion in water. However, high micro-organism concentration in high rate anaerobic reactor compensates the decreased temperature. Figure 3.2 illustrated the mean temperature values of the all the stations.

Fig. 3.2: Mean Temperature values for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Colour

The colour of the water was brownish to dark black and emitted noxious smell because of the abattoir effluent discharged into the stream. The colour of the collected samples ranged from 12TCU to 25TCU. Therefore, the value at upstream was within the WHO guideline while the values at other points were far above the stipulated of 15TCU (WHO, 2017).

Dissolved Oxygen

The mean values of dissolved oxygen of the stream ranged from 54mg/l to 120 mg/l. WHO and NSDWQ recommend dissolved oxygen at 6mg/l and 6.32mg/l respectively. This implies that the dissolved oxygen of the stream was okay and could support aquatic animals. DO concentration below 2mg/l may lead to the death of most aquatic life (Hossain and Rahman, 2022). Fig. 2.3 showed the mean values of dissolved oxygen of all the stations.

Fig. 3.3: Mean Dissolved Oxygen of all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Total Dissolved Solid

The TDS ranged from 37mg/l to 65mg/l. WHO and NSDWQ recommend 500mg/l for total dissolved solid. The concentrations of the stream were within the guidelines of (WHO, 2017 and NSDWQ, 2007).

Nitrate (NO₃): The WHO and NSDWQ recommend Nitrate at 50mg/l. The mean values for Nitrate for the sample collected ranged from 27.465mg/l to 36.723mg/l. High level of Nitrate is capable of inducing eutrophication. The result revealed that the mean values of all the stations were within the WHO guideline value of 50mg/l (WHO, 2017) and NSDWQ value of 50mg/l (NSDWQ, 2007). This means that there were no abnormal values exceeding the guidelines and the

values were satisfactory. This is in agreement with WHO guidelines of 50mg/l as Nitrate and 3mg/l as Nitrate ion were retained in 2017 convention to protect against methaemoglobinaemia in bottle-fed infants following short-term exposure. Clagman et al (2021) also reported negligible nitrate concentration in inlet waste water during experiment period. Even lower negligible concentration (<0.02mg/l) was reported by (Nwankwola et al, 2009). Studies was shown that nitrate can bring about brown blood disease in fish as well as react directly with haemoglobin in the blood of humans and other warm blooded animals produce methemoglobin which destroys the oxygen transportation ability of red cells.

Ammonia (NH₃): The mean concentrations of Ammonia ranged from 0.15mg/l to 0.26mg/l. WHO recommend 0.5mg/l. This implies that the mean was within the WHO guideline value of 0.5mg/l. therefore, Ammonia had no effect on the downstream users.

Phosphorus: The mean values of phosphorus ranged from 64.526mg/l to 76.162mg/l. The result showed that the mean values of phosphorus in all the stations were far above the WHO guideline value of 5mg/l (WHO, 2017). The result revealed that the phosphorus concentration was not satisfactory. The stream will experience explosive growth of aquatic plants which can lead to a variety of water problems including low dissolved oxygen concentration. This is an agreement with (Olanrewaju et al, 2023) that noted the elevated levels of nutrients (Nitrogen and phosphorous in surface water due to pollution accelerated the growth oxygen depleting microbes, destroy the aquatic ecosystem and result to eutrophication.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand

The mean values of BOD ranged from 38.4mg/l to 172.0mg/l. The result revealed that the mean values at all the stations were higher than WHO guideline value of less than 5mg/l for drinking water (WHO, 2017). Low level of BOD in stream systems indicates good water quality, while high levels indicate polluted water. The mean values of BOD (January to March) were higher than that of (April to June). The dry season had higher BOD results. This is justified by the high dilution activity resulted from heavy rainfall of April to June, 2024. Therefore, the mean BOD values were not satisfactory. The aquatic organisms in the stream will be affected which could lead to their death. The high BOD poses health risk and contamination of surface water from Abattoir waste constitute significant environmental hazard (Nandomah & Tetteh, 2023).

Chemical Oxygen Demand

Chemical Oxygen Demand is an important parameter used to measure the amount of organic pollutants present in water. It represents the total quantity of oxygen that is required to chemically oxidize organic and inorganic matter in the water sample. The mean values of COD ranged 182.66mg/l to 230.00mg/l. The result showed that the mean values at all the stations were higher than WHO guideline of 10mg/l for drinking water (WHO, 2017). The high COD values 182.66mg/l to 230.00mg/l in the samples recorded revealed that the stream water had high organic load. The elevated values of COD resulted from the Abattoir effluents. High COD indicates organic pollutant which can be toxic to aquatic life (Daniel et al, 2023).

Zinc: The mean values of zinc ranged from 3.783ppm to 5.632ppm. The result revealed that the mean values of zinc at all the stations were higher than WHO guidelines of 3PPM for drinking water (WHO, 2017). Therefore, the mean values of zinc were not satisfactory. The downstream concentration (3.750PPM) was still higher than WHO guideline of 3PPM. This could indicate that

the stream has a limited ability to dilute the discharged zinc, possibly due to low flow or continued contributions from surrounding areas. The fact that the downstream concentration was lower than the discharge point, could indicate same level of natural dilution effects, however, the concentration remained a concern, especially in term of regulatory limits for water quality.

Lead: The mean concentrations of lead ranged from 0.411ppm to 0.465ppm. The result showed that mean values of lead in all the stations were above the WHO guideline value of 0.01PPM (WHO, 2017) and (NSDWQ, 2007) value of 0.01PPM. The result revealed that lead concentrations were not satisfactory. Lead is a toxic heavy metal that can have serious health effects, particularly in pregnant women. Chronic exposure can lead to development issues, cognitive deficits and a variety of other health problems. The WHO and NSDWQ recommend close monitoring of stream water to ensure concentration of lead is within 0.01PPM. Danger of consuming stream polluted by lead include severe headaches, loss of co-ordination, convulsion and serious damage to kidney, liver, brain, reproductive and central nervous system.

Fig. 3.4: Mean Lead for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Aluminium

The mean values of Aluminium ranged from 2.814PPM to 5.632PPM. The result revealed that mean values of Aluminium in all stations were far above the WHO guideline value of 0.10PPM (WHO, 2017) and (NSDWQ, 2007) value of 0.2PPM. Therefore, the water is not safe for drinking. High concentration of Aluminium causes brain damage, bone diseases and severe anaemia.

Fig. 3.5: Mean Aluminium for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Mercury

Distance Downstream (M)

Fig. 3.6: Mean Mercury for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

The mean values of mercury ranged from 0.032PPM to 0.054PPM. This means that the stream is polluted at all stations because the Mercury concentrations of the stations were above the WHO guideline value of 0.01PPM (WHO, 2017) and (NSDWQ, 2007) value of 0.001PPM. Methyl Mercury, a highly toxic substance that causes neurological damage, produces chromosomal aberrations and has teratogenic effects when drinking water contaminated by Mercury.

Total Coliform Count

The mean value of Total Coliform Count ranged from 13MPN/100mg/l to 28MPN/100mg/l. The result showed that the mean values of Total Coliform Count were higher than WHO guideline of $\frac{0.2\text{MPN}}{100\text{mg/l}}$ and NSDWQ value of 10MPN/100mg/l. This means that the stream was polluted in all the stations and was not suitable for drinking. The contamination is an indicator that a health risk exists for individuals who consume the polluted stream water.

Distance Downstream (M)

Fig. 3.7: Mean Total Coliform Count for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Escherichia Coli

The mean values of E-coli ranged from $\frac{9\text{MPN}}{100\text{mg/l}}$ to $\frac{37\text{MPN}}{100\text{mg/l}}$. The result revealed that the values of E-coli were far higher than WHO guideline of $\frac{0.0\text{MPN}}{100\text{mg/l}}$ (WHO, 2017) and NSDWQ value of $\frac{0.0\text{MPN}}{100\text{mg/l}}$. This implies that the stream has indication of faecal materials of animals. Consuming the stream water untreated portends danger from water-borne diseases such as urinary tract infections, bacteraemia, meningitis, diarrhoea (one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality among children), acute renal failure and haemolytic anaemia. The detection of *Escherichia coli* provided a clear evidence of pollution and therefore highlighted the danger which the people face from the use of the stream.

Fig. 3.8: Mean Total Coliform Count for all the stations for January to June, 2024.

Conclusion

The impact of Abattoir effluent on stream water quality highlighted significant ecological concerns. The findings underscore the need for effective management practices to mitigate adverse effects on water systems and aquatic life. The study revealed that some physico-chemical concentrations of the stream were within permissible limits of WHO and NSDWQ guidelines for drinking water. But Heavy metals (Pb, Zn, Al, Hg) and Biological parameters (BOD, COD, Total coliform count and E-coli) were far above the stipulated limits of WHO and NSDWQ standards and were the critical pollutants of Iyi Eke stream. The risk of using Iyi Eke stream water bathing, washing, and drinking poses threat to children, farmers and fishers with low immunity. Thus, the water should be treated before use and effective waste management practices within the Abattoir should be enforced. The research suggests bioaccumulation in fish of Iyi Eke stream for future research

Recommendations

1. Effluent treatment system: Abattoir should invest in effective wastewater treatment systems to ensure that all effluent is adequately treated to meet WHO and NSDWQ standards prior to discharge into waterways.
2. Public Awareness and Education: It is vital to inform local communities about the potential dangers associated with contamination water bodies including health risks and appropriate measures to mitigate exposure.

3. Improved Waste Management: Abattoir should implement better waste management practices, including the treatment of effluent before discharge to minimize environmental impacts. Treatment methods might include physical, chemical and biological processes to ensure that water quality standards are met.
4. Regulatory Compliance: Authorities should enforce stricter regulations concerning the discharge of industrial effluents, particularly from abattoirs, to minimize environmental impact. This can include regular monitoring and mandatory treatment of waste before discharge.
5. Collaborative Efforts: Stakeholders such as government, environmental agencies, abattoir operators, and community leaders should collaborate to develop sustainable practices that balance industrial operations with environmental protection.
6. The study recommends biological treatment of Abattoir effluents using anaerobic digesters.

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